

Appendix 5: Three periods of the development of engineering ethics studies in the Netherlands¹

Figure 4. Three periods of the development of engineering ethics studies in the Netherlands

¹ This text is an appendix of the paper “A Comparative Institutional Analysis of Engineering Ethics in the Netherlands and the United States”.